

Canalicular adenoma of the buccal mucosa: Diagnostic and surgical insights

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Abstract

Canalicular adenoma is a benign tumor of the salivary glands that can occur in various locations within the oral cavity, with a predilection for the upper lip, but also in other regions, including the palate, parotid gland, esophagus, etc. It is characterized by oligo-symptomatic presentation and a slow growth rate. Surgical treatment is required, and histological verification is essential. Long-term follow-up is recommended for optimal management.

Keywords

canalicular adenoma, salivary gland tumor, surgical treatment

Introduction

Canalicular adenoma (CA) is a benign tumor that typically arises from the minor salivary glands and remains asymptomatic until it reaches a larger size (Thompson et al. 2015). Salivary gland tumors are relatively rare, accounting for approximately 2%–3% of all tumors. Canalicular adenoma (CA) can occur in both genders, with a slight predominance in females, at a ratio of 1.8:1 (Samar et al. 2014; Ortega et al. 2018). Canalicular adenoma (CA) accounts for 2%–6.5% of all benign lesions in the head and neck region and 1%–3% of all salivary gland tumors. Some authors have hypothesized a possible ethnic predisposition (Wang et al. 2015; Peraza et al. 2017). The upper lip is the most common location (80%), followed by the buccal mucosa, palate, tongue, floor of the mouth, and, less commonly, the larynx, parotid gland, maxillary sinus, mandible, esophagus,

and retromolar area (Dayisoğlu et al. 2012; Samar et al. 2014; Wang et al. 2015; Ortega et al. 2018).

Canalicular adenoma (CA) can present clinically in either a solitary form, which accounts for the majority of cases (87%), or a multifocal form, observed in approximately 13% of cases. Typically, the tumor manifests as a painless, submucosal swelling that increases in size progressively over time. The overlying mucosa generally appears pink to pale pink in color. However, in rare instances, it may exhibit a bluish discoloration, mimicking the appearance of a mucocele (Oliveira-Santos et al. 2012; Samar et al. 2014; Ortega et al. 2018). The diameter of CA varies between 0.5 cm and 2.0 cm (Oliveira-Santos et al. 2012; Samar et al. 2014). The lesion is typically mobile and tender and may exhibit slight fluctuation. It does not cause ulceration or any other changes and lesions to the oral mucosa (Dayisoğlu et al. 2012; Oliveira-Santos et al. 2012; Thompson et al. 2015; Ortega et al. 2018). Histologically,

canalicular adenoma (CA) is characterized by a combination of distinct structural features. These include solid areas of cellular growth, trabeculae, tubules, and cribriform or membranous patterns, where the tumor cells form a sieve-like or sheet-like arrangement (Samar et al. 2014).

Materials and methods

A 75-year-old woman with no systemic diseases and a non-smoking history was referred to an oral surgeon due to a lump in her left cheek, which had been gradually increasing in size, albeit at a slow rate. The patient reported no general or localized symptoms associated with the tumor. Upon visual examination, the lesion was located in the buccal area, near the commissure of the upper and lower lip. The lesion was identified by the patient approximately 4 years prior. The overlying mucosa appeared pale pink, without redness of the overlying mucous membrane and with a localized bluish appearance of the top of the affected area. Palpation revealed a well-circumscribed sub-mucosal formation with a soft consistency, not adhering to the surrounding tissue. Applying slight intraoral pressure made the tumorexternally visible. The site exhibited mild tenderness on palpation; no signs of lymphadenopathy were observed. Based on the patient's history, clinical presentation, and radiographic findings, a preliminary diagnosis of a benign minor salivary gland tumor was made.

Prior to the surgical procedure, informed consent was obtained from the patient. Under local anesthesia, a superficial horizontal incision was made in the mucosa directly above the tumor. This incision was extended 3–4 mm medially and distally to ensure adequate exposure for the total removal of the formation (Fig. 3a). The operative field was further extended until adequate access to the tumor was achieved (Fig. 3b1, b2). By dissection, the tumor was carefully and completely removed. The surgical site was then thoroughly inspected, and the wound surface was inspected to ensure a clean and smooth area (Fig. 3c, d). After identifying the superior labial artery (Fig. 3d), the wound edges were approximated, and primary closure was successfully achieved. The surgical site was then sutured using single interrupted stitches with 3-0 silk sutures (Fig. 3e). After the surgery, ibuprofen 400 mg three times daily was prescribed. The recovery period was uneventful. The sutures were removed 10 days post-surgery. The patient was followed up for six months, with no evidence of disease recurrence.

The whole tumor mass removed during the surgical procedure was submitted for histopathological evaluation. The diagnosis of canalicular adenoma arising from the minor salivary glands was confirmed histologically. The histological examination revealed a solid-cystic formation, encased by a fibrous capsule and surrounded by small salivary glands. The cellular composition consisted of monomorphic, cylindrical cells arranged in anastomosing trabecular structures. Immunohistochemical analysis demonstrated a characteristic GFAP (glial fibrillary acidic protein) reaction, which was confined to the periphery of the tumor.

Figure 1. Extraoral appearance of the formation.

Figure 2. Intraoral appearance of the formation.

Discussion

Canalicular adenoma is a variant of monomorphic adenoma, recognized as a separate entity in the WHO classification in 1991 (Seifert 19910). In general, the tumor is asymptomatic, but by growing, it appears as a painless mass, causing patients discomfort, pressure, and other symptoms (Peraza et al. 2017). It shows female predominance with a peak incidence in the seventh decade. In 80% of the cases, it is localized in the upper lip, followed by the hard palate (Peraza et al. 2017). The tumor is typically encapsulated, with a cut surface that is partly solid and partly cystic (Thompson et al. 2015). Histologically, the tumor comprises cystic spaces formed by interconnecting bilayered strands of uniform cuboidal or columnar cells with round to oval nuclei and eosinophilic cytoplasm. There is no outer layer of myoepithelial cells, and the stroma is not prominent, with a sclerotic or edematous appearance. Immunohistochemistry is usually not necessary for the diagnosis, but there is peculiar immunoreactivity for GFAP with characteristic peripheral distribution and negative cells in the center.

We have presented the surgical treatment of a canalicular adenoma (CA) located in the buccal mucosa of a 75-year-old female patient. Retention salivary gland cysts/mucoceleles can closely resemble tumors, making accurate

Figure 3. Surgical protocol. **a.** horizontal incision in the buccal mucosa extending mesial and distal along the formation; **b1, b2.** elongation of the incision; visualization and mobilization of the formation; **c.** extirpation; **d.** surgical site after removal of the adenoma; identification of the labial superior artery; **e.** interrupted sutures.

Figure 4. Anastomosing cords of tumor cells (H&E stain, x5).

Figure 5. Loose edematous stroma with some blood vessels (thin arrows) and bilayer cords of tumor cells (thick arrows) (H&E stain, x20).

Figure 6. A, B. GFAP showing typical peripheral reactivity with negative tumor cells in the center (GFAP, $\times 10$).

diagnosis challenging. Differential diagnosis could be made among benign mesenchymal tumors as well. To differentiate between these conditions, a biopsy is essential to establish a definitive diagnosis.

The definitive diagnosis was confirmed through excisional biopsy. While other methods of histological verification may be contraindicated, excisional biopsy is considered both safe and accurate, particularly in the differential diagnosis of other tumors and conditions such as adenoid cystic carcinoma, ameloblastoma, paraganglioma, lipoma, thrombosed blood vessels, vascular anomalies, mucocele, and others (Sivolella et al. 2014; Wang et al. 2015; Bhagde et al. 2016). The salivary gland tumors are relatively rare and represent approximately 2%–3% of head and neck neoplasms (Pereira et al. 2007; Phore et al. 2018). This benign tumor arises from minor salivary gland ductal tissue in the oral cavity, with rare appearance in the parotid gland (Pereira et al. 2007). CA represents <1% of the salivary gland tumors (Pereira et al. 2007). Usually, the CA is represented as a solitary lesion, but sometimes multiple tumors can be found (Siqueira et al. 2013). The histological findings often can resemble paraganglioma, papillary cystadenocarcinoma, benign and malignant neoplasias of glandular tissue, lipomas, mucocele, thrombosed vessel, ductal adenoma, reticulated myoepithelioma, ameloblastoma, adenomatoid odontogenic tumor, polymorphous low-grade adenocarcinoma, and skin basal cell carcinoma (Weinreb et al. 2010; Sivolella et al. 2014; Wang et al. 2015; Bhagde et al. 2016; Panagiotis et al. 2021).

The treatment of CA is surgical. The treatment protocol includes enucleation, biopsy, and excision of the tumor formation (Phore et al. 2018). CA has a recurrence rate of 5% of the surgically treated cases (Peraza et al. 2017). For this reason, long-term monitoring is essential (Bhagde et al. 2016).

Conclusion

Canalicular adenoma is a benign neoplasm that can arise in various anatomical locations within the oral

and maxillofacial region. The standard treatment for lesions in the maxillofacial region involves complete surgical excision. A definitive diagnosis is established through histopathological analysis, as the differential diagnosis encompasses both benign and malignant conditions. In this case, we present the successful surgical management of a canalicular adenoma located in the buccal mucosa of a 75-year-old woman. Long-term follow-up is recommended due to the potential, though low, risk of recurrence.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Faculty of Dental Medicine.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

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Author contributions

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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